

CLASSIFICATION AND LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRECEDENT UNITS

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Abstract: This article describes the definition and classification of precedent units based on analysis.

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Precedent units are one of the main objects of study of linguo-cultural studies, which is one of the leading areas of research of the language system. In the studies devoted to these units, it is noted that the term precedent is used for the first time in linguistics in the article “Роль прецедентных текстов в структуре и функционировании языковой личности” by Yu.N. Karaulov²¹⁰.

In Russian linguistics, personal names, stable combinations, sentences and texts, which are well known to certain language speakers and stored in their linguistic memory, are repeatedly referred to in speech activity, are recognized as precedent units²¹¹. In other words, this term is understood as “texts that are important for a person in emotional and cognitive relationships, have a personal character, that is, together with those around him, well known to his predecessors and contemporaries, references that are repeated again and again in communication²¹².” Yu.Karaulov initially included precedent names in the titles of works and quotations.

Later, O.V. Lisechenko expanded the limit of precedent names and added anthroponyms to it. In the studies of precedent units in Russian linguistics, texts belonging to the middle and lower periods of human history, such as artistic texts, myths, folk songs, fairy tales, anecdotes, proverbs, static similes, phraseology, and the names of famous persons, are noted as precedent units. It seems that the

²¹⁰ Гунько Ю.А. Особенности функционирования прецедентных высказываний в разговорной речи носителей русского языка: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. – Санкт-Петербург: Санкт-Петербургский гос.ун-т, 2002. – С. 24.

²¹¹ Красных В.В. Система прецедентных феноменов в контексте современных исследований / Язык, сознание, коммуникация. Вып. 2. – М.: Филология, 1997. – С. 5-12.

²¹² Караулов Ю.Н. Русский язык и языковая личность. – М.: изд-во МГУ, 1987. – С. 216.

researcher V.V. Krasnykh further expands the views expressed about the unit precedent²¹³.

According to him, behind the precedent units, there is always a common and necessary idea about it for all representatives of a certain national and cultural mentality, or the invariance of its acceptance, which provides a clear, understandable, connotative coloring of all references to the precedent units. In other words, precedent texts encourage interlocutors to refer to general higher-level additional knowledge, that is, knowledge that arises in a person in the process of understanding and knowing the world²¹⁴. Common knowledge characteristic of representatives of one culture is similar to each other to a certain extent, incorporating individual elements of this knowledge.

The development of society, the change of moral values also affects the mobility of the composition of precedent units. For example, precedent refers to names, phrases, situations associated with scientists (Eynshteyn, Lomonosov - precedent names), works of art, and historical events (Titanic is a precedent name, as well as a precedent situation). Today, the popularity of television is increasing, and large television projects, titles of films, books, politicians and public figures become a precedent s going Including the famous book "Harry Potter", the famous TV show "Mo'jizalar maydoni", the names of politicians who have become a precedent - Angela Merkel, Barack Obama, Donald Trump.

Antecedent nouns appear as a type of antecedent unit. Precedent units are classified by D.B. Gudkov, I.V. Zakharenko, V.V. Krasnykh and D.V. Bagaeva according to their essence, nature and characteristics as precedent texts, precedent phrases, precedent situations and precedent names²¹⁵.

Precedent text is the representation of the ideas about the known reality that were previously formed in the mind of the speaker and the listener in the form of text; special integration of popular and generalized sentences into the text. The second stanza of the talented poet Iqbal Mirza's poem "*Ман каманд истарман, тан гулхандадир, Ўзим ҳар жойдаман, кўнгил сандадир*" is taken from Muqimi's poem "*Ўзим ҳар жойдаман, кўнгил сандадир*" and matches the content and essence of the previous verses of the poem. In the science of Eastern linguopoetics, such artistic art, based on the inclusion of artistic fragments in the text of the work, is known as tazmin ("*бир нарса иккинчи бир нарса орасига кўймоқ*").

The precedent situation (case) differs from other precedent units, because with their help the speaker refers to a larger stereotype that occupies a more important

²¹³ Красных В.В. Система прецедентных феноменов в контексте современных исследований / Язык, сознание, коммуникация: Сб. статей. – М.: Филология, 1997. Вып. 2. – С. 5-12.

²¹⁴ Кристева Ю. Семиотика. – М.: МГУ, 1970. – С.170

²¹⁵ Захаренко И.В., Красных В.В., Гудков Д.Б., Багаева Д.В. Прецедентное высказывание и прецедентное имя как символы прецедентных феноменов. Язык, сознание, коммуникация. Вып. 1. – М., 1997. – С. 92.

place in the system of cultural codes, the precedent situation mentioned by the author recreates the whole event in the memory of the speaker. Reference to precedent can be made in the text through differential signs (attributes) that are part of its cognitive base. Precedent is often defined metonymically, indicating the place where the relevant event took place. For example, *Чернобил нафақат шаҳар, балки улкан экологик офатдир*. (Gazetadan)

Precedent expressions are quotations, aphorisms, proverbs, sayings, and slogans of various characters. Because the skill of the speaker is also related to the successful integration of existing literary and linguistic clichés into the composition of the work. Proverbs, sayings and proverbs that have been refined in the folklore language for centuries can be a classic example of such clichés. For example, “Минг сиз-биздан бир жиз-биз яхши” of Pahlavonquli Ravnaq skillfully used the folk proverb: *Не самар ҳосил бўлур юзда дегандан сизу биз, Яхшироқ минг сизу-биздан кўринур бир жизу-биз*.

A predicate noun is an individual name associated with a predicate text or a predicate situation, or a symbolic name denoting a set of specific attributes. Precedent names have a certain set of differentiating properties, they can consist of one or more elements. For example, the names of people: Amur Temur, Alisher Navoi, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Nadira, Zulfiya; Country and city names: Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara; geographical names: Pamir, Amudarya, Syrdarya, etc. For example, *Тилакларим бажо бўлур ва лекин сен бўлмасанг, Бамисоли Искандардай очиқ кетар қўлларим*. (А.Огіров, “Ереван кўчасида”).

In conclusion, it can be said that the precedent units are linguistic and cultural units, which are important in increasing the richness and expressiveness of the artistic text.

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